

Factors Affecting the Students' Behavior during the Eucharistic Celebration

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Abstract

The Eucharist is one of the most vital aspects of faith. As the Catechism of the Catholic Church proclaims, the Eucharist is the source and summit of the Christian life. There are considerable factors needed to promote a meaningful Celebration, and one is the active participation of the members. What do we mean by active participation? It is the utmost attention and focuses only on the celebration. However, this idea is difficult to grasp due to the overwhelming disaster that hits the world talking about the Pandemic. Many of whom have tremendously been affected by the phenomenon. Unfortunately, some have lost their faith and started doing things opposite to what they did before. This research aims to pinpoint and understand the prominent reasons that have affected individuals' participation in the Holy Eucharist. The research focuses on the basic education students at St. Paul University Surigao, and their holistic formation is involved in the Holy Eucharist. Results have shown that most students still exhibit the same passion for attending Holy Mass and are unaffected by some corresponding influences. Nevertheless, these factors are recognized so that the conflict will be resolved. Despite all, results still have shown that students are willing to attend the celebration and are open to a meaningful Holy Eucharist celebration.

Keywords: *Eucharistic Celebration, Behavior, Personal Factors, Environmental Factors.*

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Introduction

The Second Vatican Council states clearly that the “Mother Church earnestly desires that all the faithful should be led to that fully conscious and active participation in liturgical celebrations which is demanded by the very nature of the liturgy. Such participation by the Christian people as “a chosen race, a royal priesthood, a holy nation, a redeemed people” (1 Pet. 2:9; cf. 2:4- 5) is their right and duty because of their baptism. The Church, therefore, earnestly desires that Christ’s faithful, when present at this mystery of faith, should not be there as strangers or silent spectators; on the contrary, through a good understanding of the rites and prayers, they should take part in the sacred action conscious of what they are doing, with devotion and full collaboration. They should be instructed by God’s word and be nourished at the table of the Lord’s body; they should give thanks to God; by offering the Immaculate Victim, not only through the hands of the priest but also with him, they should also learn to offer themselves; through Christ the Mediator, they should be drawn day by day into ever more perfect union with God and with each other, so that finally God may be all in all.” (Sacrosanctum Concilium 14, 28)

The Eucharist is one of the most vital aspects of faith. As the Catechism of the Catholic Church proclaims, the Eucharist is the source and summit of the Christian life (cf. CCC 1324). Therefore, it is only fitting that a Catholic school gives students the regular opportunity to grow in their love and devotion to the Holy Eucharist, especially during the Holy Mass celebration. The Holy Eucharist

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celebration on campus powerfully portrays the vision and mission of St. Paul University Surigao: to educate and form Paulinians. St. Paul University Surigao faithfully reminds its students to attend the Sunday Mass regularly and invites them to celebrate the Holy Eucharist inside the campus on first Fridays and during special feasts and solemnities in response to this call to place the Eucharist at the center of its students' lives.

St. Paul University Surigao assists its students diligently in realizing this great sacrament as the foundation of their faith. Students can learn to truly realize the presence, memorial, and sacrifice of the Lord Jesus Christ for the sanctification of all by repeatedly being reminded to participate actively and to behave well with great devotion during the Holy Mass. However, there are still instances that show how the students inactively participate and misbehave during the Eucharistic celebration.

More so, recently, one incident occurred in one of the Catholic schools here in the Philippines wherein one of the Senior High School students made fun of the blessed host by doing a food review and posting it online.

Thus, these are the reasons why this study is being conducted.

Materials and Methods

Research Design

This study is descriptive in nature, as the study's objective is to know the factors that affect the students' behavior during the Eucharistic celebration in the school.

Participants

The participants will be the selected students from Grade 4 to Grade 12 of St. Paul University Surigao.

Instrument

The instrument of this study will be a researcher-made questionnaire. The researcher-made questionnaire consists of two (2) parts. The first part of the questionnaire includes the data on the participants in terms of age, sex, grade level, and years of stay at St. Paul University Surigao.

Part 2 is about the factors affecting the students' behavior during the Eucharistic celebration.

Data Gathering

The researchers sent a letter to the principal asking permission to conduct the study in the Basic Education Department of St. Paul University Surigao.

Upon approval, the researchers float the researcher-made questionnaire to the Basic Education Department of St. Paul University students. Retrieved data were tallied, tabulated, interpreted, and analyzed.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools were used to analyze the factors affecting the students' behavior during the Eucharistic celebration.

Frequency Count and Percentage Distribution. This tool was used to determine the distribution of the participants.

Mean and Standard Deviation. This tool determined the factors affecting the students' behavior during the Eucharistic celebration.

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). This tool was used to measure the significant difference in the factors affecting the students' behavior during the Eucharistic celebration when grouped according to their profile.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Profile of the Correspondents

Profile	f (n=604)	%
Grade Level		
Grade 4	9	1.49
Grade 5	47	7.78
Grade 6	34	5.63
Grade 7	125	20.70
Grade 8	75	12.42
Grade 9	67	11.09
Grade 10	54	8.94
Grade 11	179	29.64
Grade 12	14	2.32
Years in SPUS		
1 year	215	35.60
2 year	56	9.27
3 year	51	8.44
4 year	64	10.60
5 year	80	13.25
6 year	30	4.97
7 year	36	5.96
8 year	29	4.80
9 year	43	7.12

The table above shows the range of grade levels, the years of stay of students in St. Paul University Surigao, and the percentage of each group. There are 604 total correspondents. Among the grade levels, the grade 11 students have responded to the survey more than the rest of the grade levels. Out of 604 correspondents, 179 are from grade 11, garnering the highest percentage of 29.64%, while the lowest belongs to grade 4 with 1.49%. In addition, 215 out of 604 correspondents are first timers in the school, garnering the highest percentage among the group with 35.60%. In contrast, those who are in school for 8 years have only 4.80%, having the lowest percentage among the group.

Table 2. Results from the Indicators in terms of Personal and Environmental Factors

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI	QD
Personal Factors				
1. I believe that praying is girl's stuff.	2.98	1.26	Sometimes	MA
2. I believe that I am too young to understand the celebration.	2.84	1.16	Sometimes	MA
3. I believe that the Mass is only for grandfathers and grandmothers.	3.11	1.23	Sometimes	MA
4. I believe that the Eucharist is the real presence of Jesus.	2.07	1.12	Seldom	SA
5. I believe that the mass affects my life.	1.97	1.11	Seldom	SA
6. I believe that the student body must participate actively in the celebration.	1.89	1.14	Seldom	SA
7. I prefer going to mass only on Sundays.	2.39	0.96	Seldom	SA
8. I prepare myself spiritually before Mass.	2.01	1.05	Seldom	SA
9. I enjoy going to mass.	1.93	1.10	Seldom	SA
10. I enjoy praying with my classmates.	2.01	1.07	Seldom	SA
11. I enjoy the homily of the priest.	1.92	1.10	Seldom	SA
12. I have a personal devotion to the Eucharist.	2.03	0.99	Seldom	SA
13. I participated actively in the Eucharistic Celebration.	2.00	1.07	Seldom	SA
14. I behave properly during the Eucharistic Celebration.	1.92	1.10	Seldom	SA
15. I am praised by my teachers if actively participate and behave during the Eucharistic Celebration.	2.19	1.04	Seldom	SA
Average	2.22	1.10	Seldom	SA
Environmental Factors				

1. The venue has comfortable seats for each person and a good sound system.	2.06	1.04	Seldom	SA
2. The venue is big enough to house the whole school community.	2.02	1.03	Seldom	SA
3. The venue provides a prayerful ambiance.	2.01	1.08	Seldom	SA
4. The mass is held at a very convenient time.	2.01	1.07	Seldom	SA
5. The schedule of the mass helps in creating a prayerful atmosphere.	1.99	1.09	Seldom	SA
6. The schedule of the mass allows all members of the community to join the celebration.	1.98	1.08	Seldom	SA
7. My classmates help create a prayerful atmosphere.	2.14	1.00	Seldom	SA
8. My seatmates encourage me to pray more.	2.24	1.02	Seldom	SA
9. The choir sings well and makes me to pray more	1.98	1.08	Seldom	SA
10. The class advisers keep their class in order.	1.96	1.07	Seldom	SA
11. The teachers encourages students to actively participate in the celebration.	1.92	1.12	Seldom	SA
12. The teachers, sisters, and other employees are positioned strategically in such a way that they can supervise the students during celebrations.	1.91	1.09	Seldom	SA
13. The overall appearance of the priest makes me focus on praying.	2.01	1.07	Seldom	SA
14. The priest delivers his homily clearly; it had an impact on me.	1.93	1.09	Seldom	SA
15. the priest's voice is clear and audible.	1.95	1.11	Seldom	SA
Average	2.01	1.07	Seldom	SA
General Average:	2.11	1.09	Seldom	SA

Legend:

Scale	Verbal Interpretation	Qualitative Description
4	Very Affecting	Always
3	Moderately Affecting	Sometimes
2	Slightly Affecting	Seldom
1	Not Affecting at all	Never

The table above shows the results of the responses of the correspondents for every indicator. The table also provided the ratings' average mean and standard deviation. On the Personal Factor, the indicator *I believe that the Mass is only for grandfathers and grandmothers* got the highest mean of 3.11, with the Standard Deviation of 1.23 and interpreted as Sometimes and is qualitatively described as Moderately Affecting (MA). This indicator tells how students view the Holy Mass as it is for grandfathers and grandmothers. On the other hand, the indicator *I believe that the student body must participate actively in the celebration* lowest mean of 1.89, with the Standard Deviation of 1.14 and interpreted as seldom (S) and is described as slightly affecting (SA). This means the students wanted the student body to participate during the celebration.

On the Environmental Factors, the indicator *My seatmates encourage me to pray more* got the highest mean of 2.24, with the Standard Deviation of 1.02 and interpreted as seldom (S) and is described as slightly affecting (SA). This means that the students' seatmates during the Eucharistic celebration affect their behavior during the celebration. While the item indicator *The teachers, sisters, and other employees are positioned strategically in such a way that they can supervise the students during celebrations* got the lowest mean of 1.91, with a 1.09 SD and as interpreted as seldom (S) and described as slightly affecting (SA). This means that students appreciate the position and role of every employee for them to behave accordingly during the Eucharistic Celebration.

Table 3. Significant difference in the Factors Affecting the Students' Behavior during the Eucharistic Celebration

Profile	Dependent	F	p-value	Decision
Grade Level	Personal	1.53	0.145	Do not reject Ho
	Environment	1.87	0.062	Do not reject Ho
Years	Personal	1.18	0.310	Do not reject Ho
	Environment	0.73	0.664	Do not reject Ho

As presented in the table, despite the grade level and the years of stay of the students in St. Paul University Surigao, there are no affecting influences, both under the personal factor and the environmental factor, on the behavior of the students during the celebration of the Holy Eucharist. This is shown in the survey results on the students of the Basic Education department of St. Paul University Surigao.

Conclusion

Based on the study conducted on the basic education department students from grade 4 to grade 12 of St. Paul University Surigao, it is attested that at 0.05 significance level, there is no significant difference in the Factors Affecting the Students' Behavior During the Eucharistic Celebration when grouped according to their profile variables. Despite the prevailing influences, under personal and environmental factors, most students are unaffected by it. It is clearly presented in Table III. Nonetheless, students are aware of these realities and most of them have the same idea of the Eucharistic Celebration, regardless of their grade level, age, and years of stay in the school, as presented in Table II. Hence, results still have shown that students are willing to attend and are willing to have a meaningful Holy Eucharist celebration.

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Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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